

EFFECT OF THERMAL FATIGUE ON INTRALAMINAR CRACKING IN LAMINATES LOADED IN TENSION

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SUMMARY

Laminated composites subjected to a large number of thermal cycles between cryogenic to elevated temperatures close to glass transition, experience formation of intralaminar cracks, causing degradation of thermo-mechanical properties. The objective of this paper is to improve the understanding of the microdamage initiation and growth mechanisms in thermo-mechanical fatigue.

Keywords: thermal fatigue, intralaminar cracks

1. INTRODUCTION

Laminate composite structures which are increasingly used in aircraft engines and other space applications are going to be exposed during exploitation to a large number of thermal cycles in the temperature range between cryogenic up to elevated temperatures close to the glass transition, T_g . This thermal loading is often accompanied also by mechanical loads. In result intralaminar cracks and inter-layer delaminations develop during the service life and lead to formation of damage networks causing degradation of thermo-mechanical properties and increasing permeability and leakage in fuel tanks.

The effect of the microdamage state on the macroscopic mechanical properties was studied for many years and an overview of approaches is given in [1,2].

With respect to the intralaminar crack initiation and evolution, a common opinion at present is that these two phenomena take place in the low temperature part of the thermal cycle because the stresses caused by the mismatch of thermal properties of constituents on different length scales are the highest there. However, research at US AF MRL [3] has also revealed the importance of the elevated temperature during the cycle on the damage level in thermal cycling. Since at the highest temperature the material is very close to the stress free state, this effect cannot be explained by mechanics only. This is an evidence for material degradation during the exposure to high temperature. Possible reasons are the disintegration of the molecular network leading to degraded resin properties [4] or fiber-matrix interface degradation. Another relevant question is: why in mechanical cyclic loading using the same stress range (or energy release rate change) the required number of cycles to reach the same damage state is much larger than in thermal fatigue? The possible explanations lie in the stress state differences on the micro-scale (especially at laminate edges) leading to different mechanisms and number of cycles for initiation of damage entities.

The objective of this paper is to study the mechanisms of composite degradation in thermal fatigue by separating: 1) the effect of the total exposure time to high temperature (this exposure time is accumulating during the thermal cycling); 2) the effect of the number of thermal cycles where the lowest temperature cause high thermal residual stresses. This work is focused on investigation of how the composite material resistance to intralaminar cracking is degraded due to a) “thermal aging” and b) thermal cycling. Thus, these two “treatments” have been applied and the effect on the failure resistance has been expected to show up in mechanical tests. Certainly, testing could be done also on unidirectional (UD) composites instead of cross-ply laminates analyzed in this paper. However, there is a significant advantage using cross-ply laminates: a) in UD composites the laminate scale thermal stresses overlapping the fiber/resin scale stresses are missing; b) much more statistics regarding failure data from a single cross-ply specimen than from numerous UD specimens can be obtained.

The layers in the CF/EP $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminates are rather thick (the prepreg layer thickness was 0.5mm) and we expect that the cracking, which according to observed acoustic emission events was always unstable, was initiation governed. For initiation it seems to be more reasonable to use strength based approaches. Certainly, it must be mentioned that what is considered as strength on the ply scale is actually a complex process of fracture mechanics events on the micro-scale leading to building of a large defect.

2. STATISTICAL MODEL FOR FAILURE RESISTANCE DEGRADATION

Considering cross-ply laminate with a 90° -ply in which intralaminar cracks may develop, the 90° -ply can be described as consisting of M small elements (see Fig.1(a)).

Figure 1. Progressive intralaminar cracking in cross-ply laminate in tension: a) laminate with 90° -layer divided in elements; b) multiple cracking (three specimens).

The element length \hat{L} should be smaller than the ineffective length (the stress transfer zone, which is defined by stress distribution). Obviously for a specimen of length L

$$L = \hat{L}M \quad (1)$$

Under this condition only one crack can appear in each element and the maximum number of cracks is M . Each element can be visualized as a chain of very short domains with length in the transverse to fiber direction $\Delta L_i (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \infty)$. Following Weibull theory, the material has certain defect (flaw) size distribution characterized by function n_σ - the number of flaws per unit domain length, which would cause failure at stress σ (it is the transverse stress in the 90°-ply). Probability of failure of the domain of length ΔL_i in the element with length \hat{L} is proportional to the domain length

$$P_{fi} = n_\sigma \Delta L_i \quad (2)$$

The probability of the element survival P_s is the product of probabilities of survival of all small domains it consists of

$$P_s = (1 - P_{s1})(1 - P_{s2})(1 - P_{s3}) \dots = (1 - n_\sigma \Delta L_1)(1 - n_\sigma \Delta L_2)(1 - n_\sigma \Delta L_3) \dots \quad (3)$$

For small arguments ($n_\sigma \Delta L_i$)

$$e^{-n_\sigma \Delta L_i} \approx 1 - n_\sigma \Delta L_i \quad (4)$$

and (3) can be rewritten as

$$P_s \approx \exp(-n_\sigma \hat{L}) \quad \text{or} \quad P_f = 1 - \exp(-n_\sigma \hat{L}) \quad (5)$$

In an element with a reference length L_0 the number of defects, which may lead to failure at stress level σ is changing with the number of thermal or mechanical cycles N , thermal treatment (“conditioning”) and it depends on the stress level. Assuming that dependence on both variables follows power law we obtain

$$n_\sigma L_0 = f(N) \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \quad (6)$$

The function $f(N)$ can be assumed as a power function:

$$f(N) = \begin{cases} 1 & N < N_0 \\ A(T)(N - N_0(T))^r & N \geq N_0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

In (7) $A(T)$ represents the possible degradation at high temperature T . Generally speaking we have to expect that number of flaws $n = n(\sigma)$. However, experiments support assumption (see below) that in a first approximation it can be stress

independent. Substituting (7) and (6) into (5) the strength distribution (analog to Weibull distribution but accounting for degradation with number of cycles) can be written for $N \geq N_0$ as

$$P_f = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\hat{L}}{L_0} A(T) (N - N_0(T))^r \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad (8)$$

The probability of failure at certain stress of a fragment with length \hat{L} can be related to the number of cracks (broken elements) M_f over the gauge length L and the maximum possible number of cracks M over specimen length L

$$P_f = \frac{M_f}{M} \quad (9)$$

Since the linear transverse crack density ρ (cr/mm) is defined as the number of cracks over the gauge length

$$\rho = \frac{M_f}{L} \quad (10)$$

we obtain using (9) and (10)

$$\rho = \frac{M}{L} P_f = \frac{1}{\hat{L}} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\hat{L}}{L_0} A(T) N (N - N_0(T))^r \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right)\right) \quad (11)$$

It is interesting to note that by taking logarithm of (11) we obtain for the first crack (or for any other fixed crack density $\rho = const$) power law relationship between the used stress level and the number of cycles need to reach this crack density

$$(N - N_0)^r \sigma^m = const \quad (12)$$

where the value of the constant can be thermal treatment dependent.

This type of relationship for the first crack in mechanical fatigue has been observed experimentally in [5]. The number of cycles and temperature effects in the Weibull distribution demonstrated in (8) can be interpreted in a different way: They can be considered as a change of the scale parameter σ_0 in result of thermal treatment and fatigue effects. This interpretation is used in the following analysis of experimental studies.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS ON STRENGTH DEGRADATION

The thermal fatigue and degradation effects are studied on Carbon Fiber (CF) epoxy laminates manufactured using vacuum bag and hot press at 120°C. To prove that the composite undergoes degradation of tensile transverse strength and Mode I fracture toughness during thermal exposure at temperature close to T_g , laminates were subjected for 50 – 100h to temperatures close to T_g .

Another “treatment” was in the form of thermal cycling between +100°C and -100°C. It was expected that the failure resistance of the matrix will be degraded due to high temperature but also some cracks will appear as a result of cyclic fatigue due to high thermal stresses caused by low temperatures.

Finally, the “untreated” and the two types of “treated” laminates were loaded in tension up to certain strain level and unloaded to count the number of cracks by means of optical microscopy. In this way the crack density in the 90°-layer was determined after each such a step. Then the next loading–unloading step with higher maximum strain was performed and cracks counted again. The focus was on damage initiation and, since 90°-layers with large thickness were used, the propagation stress was lower than the initiation stress thus simplifying optical microscopy studies.

The curves for initiation governed crack density versus applied strain shown for [0°/90°/0°] laminate in Fig.1(b) depend on the strength distribution in the cracked layer and on the interaction between cracks which starts to be significant at high crack densities and may be accounted for as described in [6]. These curves were used to determine statistical transverse strength distribution in the ply as dependent on the thermal treatment. The statistical strength parameters for various treatments were obtained using (11) common procedure for Weibull parameter determination (double logarithms etc).

In applications of (11) the 90°-ply thickness in laminate may be very different and the value of \hat{L} has to be adjusted to it (thinner plies require smaller \hat{L}). Determining statistical parameters the [0°/90°/0°]_s laminate was used as a reference assuming that $L_0 = \hat{L}$. Damage development in treated and untreated (Ref) specimens during tensile loading is shown in Fig.2. Each presented data point is an average of at least three specimens with cracks counted over 50mm distance in the specimen middle region (further away from grips). The application of the standard technique to determination of the Weibull parameters and sufficient accuracy of the model are demonstrated in Fig.3(a) and Fig.3(b) correspondingly.

Figure 2. Micro-damage development in CF/EP cross-ply laminate during tensile loading after thermal aging at a) 100°C; b) 120°C

Figure 3. Determination of Weibull parameters using data for reference specimens: a) log-log plot for parameter identification; b) experimental data together with the fitting curve based on obtained parameters.

In this procedure the thermal and curing stresses were added to transverse mechanical stress in the 90°-layer calculated using laminate theory from know applied mechanical strain. The thermal and curing stresses were obtained measuring temperature dependence of a curvature of an unsymmetric (0°/90°₂) laminate shown in Fig.4(a).

Figure 4. Unsymmetric laminate used to determine curvature dependence on temperature: a) the geometrical shape; b) the temperature dependence

The temperature related variation of the curvature in Fig.4(b) shows that curvature is not zero at the manufacturing temperature $T=120^\circ\text{C}$.

This is due to the matrix shrinkage during curing leading to composite shrinkage in the transverse direction. By extrapolating this line until it crosses the temperature axis a “modified stress free temperature” can be obtained. This new temperature can be used to include both thermal effects and the effect of chemical shrinkage during curing. The suggested use of the thermal analogy is very convenient.

The combination of thermal and curing stresses at room temperature (RT) and at -100°C used in thermal fatigue tests in both laminates were calculated using the thermal expansion characteristics as described above. The results are presented in the Table 1.

Table 1. Residual stress (MPa) in the 90°-layer of the cross-ply laminate.

Laminate	RT	-100°C
[0°/90°/0°]s	38.4	64.5
[0°/90°]s	36.6	61.5

The variation of Weibull parameters in result of the thermal treatment is shown in Fig.5 (data reduction was performed for each specimen and the presented are the average of three specimens).

The presented results show about 20% decrease of the scale parameter with increasing temperature level and aging time. This result is in agreement with expectations from analysis presented in the theoretical section.

The results regarding shape parameter are inconclusive: there are signs of increasing scatter (smaller shape parameter), however this trend is not confirmed by the 100°C 100h data. It should be noted that the accuracy of the shape parameter determination is never very high and therefore conclusion that there are no distinctive changes and trends for this parameter seems to be more appropriate. The damage state during thermal cycling is evolving with the number of cycles as shown in Fig.6. The main reason for it is the high stress level on the fiber/matrix scale (leading to defect initiation at the edge) and also on the ply level leading to propagation of the initiated edge defects.

Figure 5. The dependence of the 90°-layer’s Weibull parameters on aging temperature and time: a) scale parameter; b) shape parameter.

Figure 6. Cracking development in thermal fatigue between +100°C and -100°C: a) small number of cycles; b) large number of cycles.

It is somewhat surprising that the damage development in the initial phase was much faster for [0°/90°/0°] with relatively thinner 90°-layer. Unfortunately test for higher number of cycles were not performed for this laminate. The cycle length for laminate shown in Fig.6(a) was about 35 min whereas for composites in Fig.6(b) about 20 min. It is not clear if it can explain slightly faster crack density increase in Fig.6(b).

Figure 7. Increase of crack density in 90°-layer in tensile test. Thermally cycled and thermally aged (100°C, 25h) specimens are tested. Data are average of three specimens.

Then the thermally fatigued specimens were subjected to increasing tensile loading at room temperature and further damage development was observed: in addition to earlier developed “thermal cracks” new cracks occurred at small stress proving that the composite resistance to damage caused by mechanical loading is reduced. The crack density curves in tensile test performed on thermally cycled specimens are shown in Fig.7.

Using these data Weibull parameters were obtained and they are presented in Fig.8.

Figure 8. Degradation of laminate scale (a) and shape (b) parameters due to thermal aging and fatigue. Data for composite that was only thermally aged (not cycled) at 100°C for 25h are also presented.

One can see that after 25 thermal cycles the scale parameter has slightly increased which could be explained by postcuring effects due to exposure to high temperature. With increasing number of thermal cycles the failure properties of the 90°-layer decrease by more than 50%. Data for specimens that were only thermally aged (not fatigued) at 100°C for 25h are also shown in Fig.8.

Figure 9. Horizontal cracks developing from transverse cracks observed at the thermally fatigued specimen edge at higher mechanical strains.

It is interesting to use it for comparison because 25h is also the total time spent at 100°C during the thermal fatigue, thus time of exposure to high temperature is the same in fatigue and aging experiment.

The shape parameter in Fig.8(b) is dramatically low for thermally fatigued specimens with values typical for “quasi-random” distribution of properties. It has to be noted that many secondary damage modes were observed at specimen edges subjected to thermal

fatigue, especially when they afterwards were loaded in tension, see Fig.9. The most typical are local delaminations and horizontal cracks shown in Fig.9. Many specimens were cut in longitudinal directions (to see damage propagation through the width) and cracks on the new surfaces (middle of the specimen) were analyzed. Whereas intralaminar crack density was practically the same as on the edge, there were no local delaminations and other secondary damage modes detected in the middle of laminate. Thus for this material the specimen edge is representative for intralaminar cracking but not for other damage modes.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of thermal aging close to glass transition temperature and the effect of thermal cycling on damage resistance in CF/EP cross-ply laminate were investigated experimentally. The “thermally treated” specimens were subjected to monotonic tensile loading and the multiple cracking in the 90°-layer was quantified using optical microscopy.

The multiple cracking data were analyzed in terms of Weibull distribution parameters. Thermal and curing stresses were evaluated using unsymmetric laminates at different temperatures.

It was shown that thermal aging decrease the Weibull shape parameter whereas the shape parameter remains almost the same as prior to aging.

The thermal cycling can introduce certain number of cracks but it leads also to general material degradation (lower failure resistance). It was demonstrated in post-fatigue tensile tests in terms of Weibull parameters.

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